

STATE SUPPORT IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is to state the forms and principles of state support for agriculture as an important function of state regulation and management of agriculture. Conclusions and author's suggestions on the implementation of state and local territorial measures to improve the mechanism of state support for agriculture are given.*

Key words: *agriculture, state regulation, support, subsidy, agro-industrial complex, preferential lending, financing, efficiency, transparency.*

ГОСУДАРСТВЕННАЯ ПОДДЕРЖКА – ВАЖНЫЙ ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА

Аннотация. *Цель статьи – изложить формы и принципы государственной поддержки сельского хозяйства как важной функции государственного регулирования и управления сельским хозяйством. Приведены выводы и авторские предложения по реализации государственных и местных территориальных мер по совершенствованию механизма государственной поддержки сельского хозяйства.*

Ключевые слова: *сельское хозяйство, государственное регулирование, поддержка, субсидирование, АПК, льготное кредитование, финансирование, эффективность, прозрачность.*

Introduction (Introduction)

Historical experience shows that the state has always had a positive or negative impact on the development of the country's agriculture. We all understand that without an effective state policy, without state support, agriculture, widespread throughout the world, will not only be able to fulfill its mission of forming a social state, but it will cease to function [3].

Regulation in agriculture is one of the main elements of the system of state regulation of the economy. The agro-industrial complex, along with other sectors of the economy, remains a non-self-regulating part of the economic system. In this regard, the policy of state regulation and support of this sector, sustainable development of agricultural production is a necessary component of ensuring food security of our country and its regions.

The level of self-sufficiency in a number of commodity products (for example, cotton fiber, grain, beef, milk, greenhouse vegetables, food ingredients and feed additives) without modernizing existing production and encouraging the construction of modernized, improved and modern enterprises without increasing the material and resource potential of local agriculture cannot be achieved.

Based on this, by the end of 2022, state-supported cotton, grain, dairy and meat breeding, vegetable growing, horticulture, technical and technological modernization were directed to the development of agricultural production. In Uzbekistan, from the state budget, relevant ministries, agro-industrial companies, holdings, local governments, as well as business entities and their founders, now have the opportunity to independently determine the priority directions of network support.

In addition, in 2020, a preferential lending mechanism for agricultural producers at a rate of up to 7% was introduced. As a result, during the year, the volume of investment loans to agricultural enterprises in Uzbekistan increased by 9.9 times compared to 2017 alone.

Analysis and results. State support for agriculture is a set of socio-economic, legislative, legal and organizational measures implemented by the state aimed at sustainable development of agricultural production and rural areas and food supply to the population [8].

The important indicators of the effective use of funds supporting agriculture by the state are the increase in the productivity and profitability of all branches of agricultural production, farmers and farms.

Implementation of the state support mechanism for business entities in modern conditions is to ensure the unity of organizational-economic, social-labor and administrative-legal processes, to form effective competitiveness of agro-industry production that guarantees food security of the country. [9, 10].

The adoption of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 and the implementation of the tasks defined in it, increasing the volume of food production through the effective use of available resources, ensuring the demand of the population in the domestic market and maintaining price stability, and economic and economic development

of agricultural producers. In order to provide financial support [1], dozens of sectoral presidential decrees and decisions have been adopted. In particular, the Resolution "On ensuring the continuity of financing of the costs of state support for agriculture" is devoted to issues that provide for a specific goal and financial support for the harvest every year. For example, in order to finance the expenses related to the state support of agriculture, it is envisaged to use the financing of the state support fund for agriculture at the expense of the Recovery and Development Fund, the extension of the repayment of loans given by commercial banks, and other financial support and benefits [2].

Conclusions and suggestions

1. It is necessary to revise the principles of implementation of the agricultural policy of Uzbekistan, to increase the attention to the comprehensive development of regions, in contrast to the stimulation of individual sectors and sub-sectors of the agro-industrial complex. Improving the existing laws and adopting new ones that ensure the agrarian sector of the economy, the implementation of agricultural policy measures and the effective performance of the functions of the Ministry of Agriculture.

2. We believe that the revision of the structure of agricultural policy measures should be focused on increasing the effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism of the agro-industrial complex in the following directions: credit and tax policy; price and income regulation; scientific and information services for agriculture; quality control and food safety; food aid to the population; optimization of the use of natural resources; expanding the scope of providing scientific and scientific-technical services to agriculture.

3. To provide advice on state support to the economic entities of the agro-industrial complex, state support to agricultural production related to the acceptance and processing of documents, to expand and publicize the activities of the "Agrosubsidy" system portal.

4. Providing the opportunity to apply and interact with the bodies responsible for the implementation of state support measures through the "State Services" portal.

5. Strengthening the possibility of independent choice of participation of regions in the co-financing of state programs that meet the priorities of regional development at the legislative level.

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